

Gas as surfactant in three-phase systems from methane, *p*-xylene and water: neutron imaging and molecular dynamics

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SI-1: Role of *p*-xylene polarity on *p*-xylene/water interfacial tension and affinity of methane

The energy of water/*p*-xylene interface, i.e., interfacial tension (IFT), is directly evaluated from equilibrium simulation of two phase system utilizing the pressure tensor. To validate our model for water/*p*-xylene interface, we aim to reproduce not only the absolute value of IFT but also its temperature dependence (see left and right panels of Figure S1). We relied on TIP4P/2005 water model, which reproduces well water structure, thermodynamics and phase behavior. For *p*-xylene, united-atom TraPPE FF was used at first (for consistency with our earlier work [1]). However, we have observed that the IFT is too large (~ 56 mN/m at 298 K) while the temperature dependence [2] is in fair agreement with experimental data [~ 0.1 mN/(m · K)]. In contrast, the all-atom representation of *p*-xylene (see MD Methods) resulted to reasonable IFT ~ 30 mN/m at 298 K, but the sensitivity to temperature changes was completely lost.

The major difference between the two parameterizations is that in TraPPE FF all beads carry zero partial charge, while in all atom representation partial charges on carbon and hydrogen atoms are on the order of few tenths of elementary charge (see Table S1).

We note that all *p*-xylene models phase separate with water, i.e., within numerical accuracy of our calculations are water and *p*-xylene virtually immiscible (see Figure S2). On the quantitative level, the interface is sharper for completely uncharged *p*-xylene and the mutual penetration to the subsurface of the other phase is the largest, when full partial charges on *p*-xylene are employed. If we quantify the width of the interface by the region where

normalized density increases from 0.1 to 0.9, the width of the interface rises from 0.4 nm (uncharged *p*-xylene) to 0.6nm (full partial charges on *p*-xylene).

Further, methane interactions are not directly affected by *p*-xylene parameterization, since methane is treated at united-atom level as a single uncharged LJ sphere, i.e., methane is not involved in electrostatic interactions.

Figure S3 summarizes propensity of methane to water/*p*-xylene interface at $T = 283$ K in terms of particle density profiles (left panels) and normalized density profiles (right panel). The *p*-xylene/water interface is always located at $z=0$, with *p*-xylene phase on the left (dashed lines) and water phase on the right (dotted lines, divided by 10). The top panel (Figure S3a) illustrates the role of *p*-xylene parameterization (see the legend) on interfacial affinity of methane (full lines) at fixed concentration, $x_{\text{Me}} = 0.15$. Methane is enriched at the interface if *p*-xylene is fully uncharged (black line), surface neutral at ca half of the full charges, and depleted from the interface at full partial charges on *p*-xylene.

The evolution of partial density profiles with increasing content of methane in *p*-xylene phase are shown for the uncharged *p*-xylene in the middle row (Figure S3b), and for the full partial charges on *p*-xylene in the bottom row (Figure S3c). Our hypothesis is that at full partial charges on *p*-xylene, the interface still a liquid mixture, containing water which prohibits the presence of methane molecules, while if the *p*-xylene charges are low, the interfacial water is more disorders (more like vapor phase water) allowing methane to enter the interfacial region. Another argument is based on total mass density profile, right panel of Figure S2.

The surface excess/depletion of methane at different methane concentrations and for different partial charges of *p*-xylene determined from density profiles in Figure S3 is shown on the left axis of Figure S4 and recalculated to change in IFT (right axis). Although the interfacial activity of methane qualitatively change with *p*-xylene parameterization, the quantitative effect of methane on IFT is marginal $\pm 1\text{mN/m}$ at highest methane contents ($x_{\text{Me}} \approx 0.3$).

Figure S1. Comparison of the temperature dependence of interfacial tension for water/*p*-xylene for series of all-atom *p*-xylene parameterizations, where the partial charges are globally scaled by the scaling factor (1 = partial charges of the original FF, 0 = zero partial charges) as indicated by the legend. The relative changes with temperature are compared in the left panel, the absolute values are compared in the right panel. Simulations were compared at external pressure $p = 50$ bar.

Figure S2. Left panel presents the comparison of the shapes of normalized partial density profiles of water (full lines) and *p*-xylene (dashed lines) in the vicinity of water/*p*-xylene interface for a series of partial charges on *p*-xylene molecule (see the legend and Table S1, 1 = partial charges of the original FF, 0 = zero partial charges) at $T = 283$ K. The Gibbs dividing surface is for convenience located at $z_{\text{GDS}} = 0$. The sharpening of the interface with reducing partial charges on *p*-xylene (thus promoting its nonpolar character) is clearly documented. Total mass density close to the interface is shown in the right panel.

Figure S3. Overview of methane affinity (partial density profile) to the water/*p*-xylene interface at $T = 283$ K. Partial densities of methane (full line), water (dotted line, divided by 10) and *p*-xylene (dashed line). Top row (a), variation of methane affinity with reducing partial charges (see Table S1) on *p*-xylene molecule at selected concentration of methane ($x_{\text{Me}} = 0.15$) in *p*-xylene phase. Middle row (b), results for *p*-xylene with zero partial charges, evolution of partial density profiles with increasing content of methane in *p*-xylene phase. Bottom row (c), results for *p*-xylene with original partial charges, evolution of partial density profiles with increasing content of methane in *p*-xylene phase.

Figure S4. Role of partial charges in *p*-xylene molecule (see the legend, 1 = partial charges of the original FF, 0 = zero partial charges) on excess of methane at water/*p*-xylene interface (left axis) and on IFT (right axis). Data are shown at $T = 283$ K and at external pressure $p = 50$ bar.

Table S1: Parameterization of *p*-xylene molecule, name, mass, Lennard-Jones parameters, and partial charges. Partial charges vary from Full ($s = 1.0$) to Zero ($s = 0$), as is used in simulations, which are discussed in this section. The molecular structure of *p*-xylene with atom names is attached for clarity.

	atom_name	Mass [a.u.]	σ [nm]	ϵ [kJ/mol]	Full ($s = 1.0$) [e]	$s = 0.9$ [e]	$s = 0.75$ [e]	$s = 0.5$ [e]	$s = 0.25$ [e]	Zero ($s = 0$) [e]
1	C00	12.01	3.50E-01	2.76E-01	-0.2	-0.17	-0.14	-0.1	-0.05	0
2	C01	12.01	3.55E-01	2.93E-01	-0.09	-0.08	-0.06	-0.04	-0.02	0
3	C02	12.01	3.55E-01	2.93E-01	-0.15	-0.13	-0.11	-0.07	-0.04	0
4	C03	12.01	3.55E-01	2.93E-01	-0.15	-0.13	-0.11	-0.07	-0.04	0
5	C04	12.01	3.55E-01	2.93E-01	-0.09	-0.08	-0.06	-0.04	-0.02	0
6	C05	12.01	3.50E-01	2.76E-01	-0.2	-0.17	-0.14	-0.1	-0.05	0
7	C06	12.01	3.55E-01	2.93E-01	-0.15	-0.13	-0.11	-0.07	-0.04	0
8	C07	12.01	3.55E-01	2.93E-01	-0.15	-0.13	-0.11	-0.07	-0.04	0
9	H08	1.01	2.50E-01	1.26E-01	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0
10	H09	1.01	2.50E-01	1.26E-01	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0
11	H0A	1.01	2.50E-01	1.26E-01	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0
12	H0B	1.01	2.42E-01	1.26E-01	0.15	0.13	0.11	0.07	0.04	0
13	H0C	1.01	2.42E-01	1.26E-01	0.15	0.13	0.11	0.07	0.04	0
14	H0D	1.01	2.50E-01	1.26E-01	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0
15	H0E	1.01	2.50E-01	1.26E-01	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0
16	H0F	1.01	2.50E-01	1.26E-01	0.09	0.08	0.07	0.05	0.02	0

17	H0G	1.01	2.42E-01	1.26E-01	0.15	0.13	0.11	0.07	0.04	0
18	H0H	1.01	2.42E-01	1.26E-01	0.15	0.13	0.11	0.07	0.04	0

SI-2: Illustration of the equivalence between surface excess and change in surface tension – water/methane

On an example of surface tension of water in the presence of methane gas we demonstrate two equivalent evaluations of surface tension from the MD simulation data. The macroscopic route utilizes pressure tensor, while the microscopic route employs the structural data, such as methane surface excess and non-ideality in the gas phase.

Figure S5 presents series of partial density profiles of methane across the water/methane interface. Defining the Gibbs dividing surface (based on water density profile), surface excess of methane (Γ_{21}) is calculated via Eq. (9). This enters Eq. (8), and, following the steps in Figure S6, allows us to evaluate change in surface tension. These results are compared to values of surface tension determined directly from pressure tensor via Eq. (8), see Figure S6, panel d.

Figure S5. Partial density profiles of methane (full lines) and water (dashed lines) across the water/methane interface at 298 K and series of methane pressures (see the legend). The left panel presents the number densities (note that water density is divided by 10 to be on the same scale). The densities in the right panel are normalized to their bulk values in order to easily compare the relative surface excess under different methane pressures.

Figure S6. Comparison of the change in surface tension of water in contact with methane gas (p_{Me} ranges from 10 to 100 bar) as determined directly from pressure tensor and indirectly from density profiles and surface excess.

Panel a (top left) presents the surface excess of methane and nonlinear (Langmuir-like) fit. The surface excess data were evaluated from density profiles, such as in Figure S5, using Eq. (9).

Panel b (top right) presents methane concentration normalized surface excess (full lines) and this term multiplied by methane nonideality correction (dashed lines), representing the right hand side of Eq. (8).

Panel c (bottom left) presents the integral of the $(-1\times)$ integrand shown in **Panel b**, which equals to the change in surface tension in $k_B T$ units.

Panel d (bottom right) evaluated changes in surface tension, with (dashed lines) and without (full lines) the methane gas nonideality correction. These results are compared to data (points), which present changes of surface tension directly calculated from the pressure tensor. The full lines are shown only for the lowest (black) and the highest (gray) temperature for clarity.

Figure S7. Fugacity coefficient (ϕ) of methane in the range of investigated methane densities in the gas phase (i.e., methane pressures in the range 10-100 bar) and temperatures (283-353 K, see the legend). Data at lowest pressures are scattered due to relatively large pressure fluctuations and were not used in linear fits of the data. The inset shows the temperature dependence of 2nd virial coefficient B_2 . These fugacity coefficients were used in $\Delta\gamma$ calculations is Figure S6.

SI-3: Surface excess and change in surface tensions for *p*-xylene:methane

Applying the protocol from SI-2 on *p*-xylene/methane interface, we connect the methane surface excess with the *p*-xylene surface tension and compare it with the direct results obtained from pressure tensor. For clarity reasons, we present results only at standard temperature $T = 298$ K. We confirmed the experimental observation, that although methane is quite soluble in *p*-xylene ($H \approx 400$ bar), it is surface active. It is noteworthy that the surface tension suppression (i.e., surface activity) by methane is larger for *p*-xylene than for water at same methane pressures (i.e., methane density in the gas phase). Methane nonideality in the gas phase is accounted for by methane fugacity coefficient ϕ , as shown in Figure S7.

Figure S8 presents series of partial density profiles of methane across the *p*-xylene/methane interface. Defining the Gibbs dividing surface (based on *p*-xylene density profile), surface excess of methane (Γ_{21}) is calculated via Eq. (9). Example of surface excess evaluation is shown in Figure S12. This enters Eq. (8), and, following the steps in Figure S9, allows us to evaluate change in surface tension. These results are compared to values of surface tension determined directly from pressure tensor via Eq. (7), see Figure S9, panel d.

Figure S8. Partial density profiles of methane (full lines) and *p*-xylene (dashed lines) across the *p*-xylene/methane interface at 298 K and series of methane pressures (see the legend). The left panel presents the number densities. The densities in the right panel are normalized to their bulk values in order to easily compare the relative surface excess under different methane pressures.

Figure S9. Comparison of the change in surface tension of *p*-xylene in contact with methane gas (p_{Me} from 10 to 100 bar, i.e., ρ_{Me} from 0.26 to 2.8 nm^{-3}), as determined directly from pressure tensor and indirectly from density profiles and surface excess.

Panel a (top left) presents the surface excess (Γ_{21}) of methane and nonlinear (Langmuir-like) fit. The surface excess data were evaluated from density profiles, such as in Figure S8, using Eq. (9).

Panel b (top right) presents methane concentration normalized surface excess (full lines) and this term multiplied by methane nonideality (dashed lines), representing the right hand side of Eq. (8).

Panel c (bottom left) presents the integral of the $(-1\times)$ integrand shown in **Panel b**, which equals to the change in surface tension in $k_B T$ units.

Panel d (bottom left) evaluated changes in surface tension, with (dashed lines) and without (full lines) the methane gas nonideality correction. These results are compared to data (points), which present changes of surface tension directly calculated from the pressure tensor.

SI-4: Determination of macroscopic properties of a poorly soluble component

When macroscopic properties of poorly soluble component (e.g., diffusion, partial molar volumes, volume fractions) should be evaluated from bulk MD simulations, it is important to assure that homogeneous phases are simulated. The extensive presence of associates (either permanent or transient) would cause erroneous determination of macroscopic properties from simulation data. For solutions, which contain small molecules, the convenient indicator of self-association is the radial distribution function (RDF), which tailing indicates formation of larger structures. For series of concentrations RDFs of a poorly soluble molecules were calculated. The results for are summarized in Figure S9.

Figure S10a (left) presents methane dissolved in water. It was found that up to $x_{\text{Me}} \approx 2\text{mol.}\%$ (i.e., $p_{\text{Me}} \approx 600$ bar as $H \approx 30\,000$ bar), methane behaves as a well dissolved gas. However, when sufficient number of molecules is available transient and at higher concentration even permanent methane nanobubbles are formed. The indication is high peak and broad shoulder in RDF at $x_{\text{Me}} = 0.1$ (i.e., 250 methane molecules in the simulation box).

Figure S10b (middle) presents *p*-xylene dissolved in water, where apply similar situation. *p*-xylene forms associates, when sufficient number of *p*-xylene molecules are available to form a hydrophobic core. In our simulation setup, the high peak and broad shoulder in RDF is observed already at $x_{\text{pXY}} = 0.02$ (50 *p*-xylene molecules in the simulation box).

Figure S10c (right) presents water dissolved in *p*-xylene. In this system, even at the lowest, but finite concentration of water ($x_{\text{water}} = 0.01$, 5 water molecules in the simulation box), water molecules strongly interact with each other (via H-bond networks) and form stable associates (identified by high peak in water-water RDF ≈ 200 , compared to ≈ 4 in pure water). The diffusion coefficient would be proportional to a droplet size. Therefore, to gather sufficient statistics for this system, we used extensive sampling (10 x 100 ns) of a single water molecule in *p*-xylene phase (i.e., infinite dilution approach).

Figure S10. Radial distribution functions (RDF) for poorly miscible molecules in given solvents. Tailing in RDFs indicates a self-association and formation of large-size objects, providing the threshold for determination of conditions of stable homogeneous systems. Left panel presents methane-methane self-association in water, middle panel *p*-xylene-*p*-xylene self-association in water, and right panel water-water self-association in *p*-xylene. We note that for water as solvent 1 mol.% means 25 molecules, while for *p*-xylene as solvent 1 mol.% means 5 molecules in the simulation box.

SI-5: Density profiles of studied interfaces

Figure S11. Normalized z -density profiles of methane (black), p -xylene (red) and water (blue) in the vicinity of interfaces of the studied systems. p -xylene/methane(gas) is in full line, water/methane(gas) is in dashed line. p -xylene with dissolved methane/water is in dot-dashed for zero partial charges on p -xylene and double-dot-dash for full partial charges on p -xylene. All systems correspond to equilibrium methane pressure $p_{\text{Me}} \approx 50\text{bar}$.

The densities of water and p -xylene are normalized to their bulk values, that of methane is normalized to the density in the gas phase (directly shown for p -xylene/methane and water/methane, and indirectly applied indirectly for p -xylene with dissolved methane/water. This representation simplifies the comparison of the relative surface excess of methane in different systems, as well as the comparison of structures at the interface.

SI-6: Illustration of surface excess - *p*-xylene/methane

Figure S12. Normalized z -density profiles of methane (red), p -xylene (black) in the vicinity of the p -xylene/methane(gas) interface at $T = 298$ K and $p_{\text{Me}} \approx 100$ bar (i.e., $\rho_{\text{Me}} \approx 2.8 \text{ nm}^{-3}$). Gibbs dividing surface (GDS) is located at $z = 0$ and the red area under the methane curve defines the surface excess (Γ) on the side of p -xylene phase ($z < 0$) and on the methane gas phase ($z > 0$). The running integral of surface excess is shown in green.

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